

TOURISM FACILITIES OF BUKHARA REGION

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Abstract. *This article contains information about tourism facilities of Bukhara region.*

Keywords: *Bukhara Palace, Zargaron Plaza, Sultan, Labi Pool, Modarikhan*

ТУРИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ОБЪЕКТЫ БУХАРСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ

Аннотация. *В данной статье содержится информация о туристических объектах Бухарской области.*

Ключевые слова: *Бухарский дворец, Заргарон Плаза, Султан, Лаби Пул, Модарихан*

INTRODUCTION

The tourism industry is one of the leading sectors of the world economy and is a promising sector that brings high income to the national economy. Tourism accounts for about 5% of the world's gross domestic product, almost 10% of the population in developed countries is employed in tourism. The tourism sector is one of the industries that suffered the biggest losses due to the COVID-19 pandemic. According to the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), in 2020, international tourism fell by 72%, or revenues from tourism services by \$1.1 trillion, to the level of 1990. As a result, 935 billion lost export earnings in the amount of dollars [12]. It is known that our country was closed for foreign and domestic tourists from March 16, 2020. As a result, more than 1,500 tour operators and 1,200 hotels stopped their activities. These, along with guides, national handicrafts, shrines and sanatoriums, catering, transport, etc., seriously affected the income of more than 250,000 people [14]. There are more than 7,300 objects of cultural heritage in Uzbekistan, such as historical monuments, monuments built by the great talent of our great ancestors, sacred sites, and most of them are included in the UNESCO list. Therefore, in recent years, our country has adopted many regulatory legal documents on the development of this direction. In particular, according to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the state management system in the fields of tourism, sports and cultural heritage" No. PF-6199, a Cultural Heritage Agency was established under the Ministry of Tourism and Sports. The fact that the main tasks of the agency, such as the identification, accounting, protection and promotion of the objects of material cultural heritage, such as maintaining the state register, electronic catalog, state cadastre, defining the protected areas, and implementing state control in the field, contribute to the further development of historical and cultural tourism in our country. It is important to carry out systematic scientific and methodological research. Thus, it is important to analyze the current state of historical and cultural tourism, its development prospects and its impact on the national economy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Bukhara is one of the oldest cities in the world. In 1997, the city celebrated its 2500th anniversary. The name Bukhara was first mentioned by the historian Narshahi in the 9th century. Before that, the city had several other names. According to many historians and linguists, the word Bukhara comes from the Sanskrit word "vihara" which means "fortress".

Based on the results of archaeological excavations, scientists came to the conclusion that this city played an important role in the economic and cultural life of the region in the period before Christ. Bukhara is located at one of the most important crossroads of the Great Silk Road from China to Rome. Islam was introduced here as a result of the Arab invasion in the 8th century. Gradually, Bukhara became the most important religious center and was increasingly called "Bukhara Sharif". During its development, the city was destroyed and rebuilt several times (by Persians, Arabs, Mughals). The unique economic and cultural development of Bukhara coincides with the times of the Somonites and Shaybanites. Bukhara is famous for its rich intangible heritage - old things, unique architectural monuments, handicrafts, scholars who made an incomparable contribution to world science. More than seventy hotels such as "Bukhara Palace", "Zargaron Plaza", "Sultan", "Labi Pool", "Modarikhan" are operating here.

Among the more than twenty tourism companies here, there are more and more private organizations that cooperate with similar structures abroad on the exchange of tourists, and at the same time have their own hotels and transport. Currently, more than four hundred people are working in tourism enterprises. All the conditions have been created for the guests coming to Bukhara to familiarize themselves with the architectural monuments, artifacts related to the national crafts of our people, jewelry, goldsmithing, and embroidery schools. The tourist service program is diverse, and cultural entertainment has a special place in it. In Nadir Devonbegi madrasa, foreigners can enjoy the performances of the folklore troupe organized in cooperation with the Regional Department of Culture and Sports, and enjoy the collections of our national clothes. Theatrical shows representing our national traditions and rituals are staged in the "Gulomjon Karvonsaroyi". "Silk and Spices" festival has been held in Bukhara for several years. This event, which has turned into a presentation of the development of our crafts, where traditions and methods have been restored, and serves to exchange experience of industry workers, is of great importance in the development of tourism and attracting foreign tourists to our country. The number of tourists coming to the region is increasing as a result of the work carried out to bring tourism to the level of modern requirements. In 1995, 10,000 foreign tourists visited Bukhara, and in 2013, this number exceeded 115,000, confirming our opinion. Current Bukhara (about 300,000 inhabitants) is divided into old and new cities like other cities of Uzbekistan. But our city has an undoubted advantage. If in other places, the old part of the city has only historical monuments and is considered an open-air museum because there are no inhabitants, in Bukhara people live as they did thousands of years ago. It allows everyone to imagine the rich history of the city. Administrative buildings, schools, institutes and industrial enterprises are located in the new part of the city. You can wander the narrow streets of 2,500-year-old Bukhara and enjoy the luxurious buildings with domes and small mud houses. The Ismail Somoni mausoleum, built in the 10th century, is one of the oldest and most beautiful monuments in Bukhara. It still looks as beautiful as it did 1000 years ago. The Somonites were the first Tajik rulers of Persian origin (875-999 AD). They built a great state with Bukhara as its capital. This period is characterized by a high level of development of specific sciences such as construction, arts, mathematics, geometry, and physics. Ismail Somoni Mausoleum The Ismail Somoni Mausoleum in Bukhara was the first building built according to exact calculations in the territory of Bukhara city. All scientists are still amazed at how logical and at the same time beautiful these calculations turned out. Ripe fingerlings picked at steep, condalang, steep angles are illuminated by different degrees of sunlight. The walls of the mausoleum resemble a

decorative box or sometimes a basket made of willow twigs. If you travel to Bukhara, you should definitely visit this monument. The people of Bukhara think that if you haven't seen the mausoleum, you haven't seen Bukhara. Ark Castle Ark Castle was the official residence of the rulers of Bukhara for hundreds of years. It is built on an artificial hill with a height of 16-20 meters. The area of the castle is about 4 hectares. People often called it a "city within a city" because it had all the things of a normal city, streets, narrow streets, palaces, mosques, workshops. The castle was destroyed, repaired and restored several times. Unfortunately, by now, little remains of the luxurious Ark of the sixties.

Many buildings were destroyed during the tyranny of the 1920s. You will hear a lot of interesting information about the history of the city, national customs and traditions in the local history museum located in the arch. In addition, standing on the high walls of the fortress, you can watch the beautiful view of Bukhara. "Poi Kalon" memorial complex is a place that attracts the attention of all visitors. "Kalon Minara", which was built in the 12th century, long before the Mongol period, can be seen from almost everywhere. In the 16th century, the Kalon Mosque and the Miri Arab Madrasah were built next to it. During Muslim holidays, the voice of the muezzin calling Muslims to prayer could be heard from the top of the minaret. In ancient times, the fire lit on top of the tower at night could be seen from afar. Now, as before, the tower is located in the old city. The tower attracts your attention from afar with its harmonious forms and clear lines. If you are lucky enough to see the tower, you will be fascinated by its precise proportions and beautifully hand-picked bricks. The Kalon Mosque is the second largest mosque in Central Asia after the Bibikhanim Mosque in Samarkand. There is little evidence that 10,000 people can fit into the mosque during the Muslim holiday. The large open-air courtyard of the mosque, its magnificent facades and covered verandas give an unforgettable impression. Due to its proportions and symmetry, the Miri Arab Madrasah, located opposite the Kalon Mosque, has always served as a model for the mosques built after it. The Miri Arab Madrasa, where the future imams were educated, was the only madrasa that functioned during the former Soviet Union for many years. Labi Khovuz is the center of Bukhara (16-17 centuries). Labi Khovuz is a favorite place of Bukhara residents and guests. Here you can meet old friends and make acquaintances with new friends, reminisce about the sixties and think about the future. There is a large pond in the middle of the square, around which various buildings have been built: Kokaldosh madrasa, Nadir Devonbegi madrasa and a house. The oldest building here is the Kokaldosh madrasa. In the 16th century, a minister named Kokaldosh ordered the construction of the largest madrasa in Central Asia in Bukhara. The construction of a caravan palace has started in the area where the Nadir Devonbegi madrasa is located. Later, Nadir Devonbegi's plans changed and the caravanserai was converted into a madrasa. This had negative consequences: there was neither a mosque nor a lecture hall for students - they were not planned. But this building is beautifully decorated with glazed ceramic and porcelain tiles. In Bukhara, you can see images of the legendary Semurg bird and the sun with a human face only on the facade of this madrasa. In the warm season of the year, you can enjoy a folklore show in the courtyard of the madrasa. Tim black night sky, treasure and happy charming melody. Could you imagine "Thousand and One Nights" differently? On the other side of the pond is a small hotel for dervishes - Nadir Devonbegi Khanaqosi.

RESULTS

Bukhara was the center of Islam in Central Asia. Many pilgrims came here who needed a room to stay the night. Therefore, there were many small hotels and caravanserais in the city. These houses were popular among religious people because they had not only rooms for sleeping, but also a large mosque for praying. The tastefully decorated door is reflected in the pool water. Come to the pool "Labi khouz". Have a cup of tea at the teahouse here. Here you will feel the beauty of the city, the hospitality of its people more than anywhere else. About 4 km outside the city is the summer palace of the last emirs of Bukhara. The palace is poetically named as "Sitorai Mokhi Khosa" - the place between the moon and the stars. The architectural structure of the palace is interesting only because it shows the taste of the rich people of the late 19th and early 20th centuries.

Most of the buildings are built in a mixed style of different views. The throne room is exceptionally decorated according to national traditions. The exquisitely delicate "ganch" carving on it will be etched in your memory. Now there is a museum of folk art, where you can see beautiful silk embroidery, ceramics, traditional women's jewelry, national clothes, etc. Bukhara is three thousand years old and one of the city that has made an incomparable contribution to world civilization. The description of this place, which has been a place of knowledge and culture since ancient times, has spread to the whole world. After the independence our President's great work was done to restore and develop national values, preserve cultural heritage, especially historical monuments, and pass them on to future generations. Ancient monuments such as Kalon Mosque, Chorbakr, Ark Castle were repaired and restored to their original appearance. Shrines of Sufism figures, founders of the Naqshbandiya, Abdulkhaliq Gijduvani, Bahouddin Naqshband, were improved by direct initiatives of President I.Karimov.

DISCUSSION

In particular, the cultural center of Bukhara occupies a special place in the framework of creative works. The 107-hectare cultural center built on the initiative and idea of the President consists of large buildings - a 700-seat regional musical drama theater, an amphitheater for 2,000 spectators, and between them the "Old and Eternal Bukhara" monument. Corridors starting from different corners of the cultural center lead to the 18-meter-high "Old and Eternal Bukhara" monument. The monument was made by the famous sculptor, artist of Uzbekistan Ilhom Jabbarov. As you climb the stairs to the monument, you will notice the gilded tiles around the monument. It means that the soil of Bukhara is equal to gold. Because Bukhara has always been a place rich in gold. Original and pure gold deposits, yombs are found here. The monument expresses the idea that one should bow not only to the golden land of Bukhara, but also to its selfless, hardworking people who made Bukhara a noble city. The people of this earth were famous for their good deeds. The great scientist Abu Ali ibn Sina, the historian Narshahi, Imam Bukhari, who made an incomparable contribution to the development and culture of the Islamic religion, scholars of the sect Abdulkhalik Gijduvani, Bahauddin Naqshband, Khwaja Arif Regari, Khwaja Mahmud Anjir Fagnawi, as well as the literature of our nation. , Ahmed Donish, Sadridin Ainiy, Abdurauf Fitrat, Faizulla Khojayev, who left a worthy mark in the development of culture, and other original children of our people have grown up. Their names are engraved in golden letters on the monument. Above these writings, the hadith "Learning knowledge is obligatory for every Muslim man and woman" is written in Uzbek, Arabic and English languages. Our ancestors and their successors today made this call the meaning of life.

Moreover, Bukhara is famous in the world as a place of knowledge and enlightenment. In the same place, the images of the architectural monuments of Bukhara's antiquity - Magoki Attar, Ismail Somoni, Chorbakr, Minarai Kalon, Ark Castle, Labihovuz, Chorminor, Bahouddin Naqshband Mausoleum and other monuments are engraved on the stone. "Dil ba yoru, dast ba kor" - this wisdom of the great Bahauddin Naqshband written on the monument calls the present generation to follow this call as it stands out as a unique example of the great spiritual heritage left by our wise ancestors. In the center of the monument, the sketches of which were prepared based on the ideas of the President, three generations - a happy young family - father, mother and child, grandfather and grandson planting tree, and father and son building a house.

CONCLUSION

There is a deep philosophy in this: life is literary, life is fleeting, good deeds of a person remain forever, in this world, a person should do good deeds, think about the future of his children, the future of his country. A huge rotating globe, 5 meters high and 32 tons in weight, installed on top of the monument, can be seen from far away. All in all, in researching the possibilities of effective use of historical and cultural tourism monuments, ways of increasing their effective use, factors affecting them and their identification, and in evaluating the possibilities of using tourist resources, it is necessary to divide resources into groups and indicate the activities of their preservation and restoration. It is necessary to determine the indicators

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